

MODEL FOR MATRIX CRACKING IN HYBRID UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

An analytical model of matrix cracking is derived for unidirectional hybrid brittle-matrix composites reinforced by two different types of aligned continuous fibre whose failure strains exceed that of the matrix. Preliminary calculations for low volume fraction composites indicate that hybrid reinforcement significantly increases the matrix cracking stress.

Keywords: Matrix cracking stress, hybrid composite.

ABSTRACT

The reinforcement of a brittle-matrix by continuous aligned fibres having a failure strain that exceeds the failure strain of matrix, can increase significantly the stress at which matrix cracking is observed in such composites. Matrix cracking in brittle materials such as glass, cement and ceramics, is usually accompanied by fibre/matrix debonding and frictional interfacial slip. The first theoretical model to explain such behaviour quantitatively was derived in the seminal paper by Aveston, Cooper and Kelly [1] (often referred to as the ACK model) who assumed that the interfacial shear stress in the region of frictional slip has a constant value that is regarded as a material property. The ACK model has been applied very widely in the literature and has led to a significant increase in the understanding of micro-cracking in composite materials. Kakemi and Hannant [2] have used some of the principles on which ACK theory is based to formulate a strength-based model of hybrid continuous fibre reinforced brittle matrix composites. They considered low volume fraction composites where polypropylene nets and bundles of glass fibres reinforced a cement matrix. Such composites are of interest to the construction industry. Each type of fibre/matrix interface is assumed to have a different value for the interfacial shear stress that arises when frictional slip occurs following debonding. Their work has stimulated the development of the energy-based analytical model, rather than a strength-based numerical model, of stress transfer that is the subject of this paper.

Following Kakemi and Hannant [2], preliminary calculations assume that the volume fraction of matrix is fixed at $V_m = 0.94$ while the volume fractions of glass fibre considered are in the range $V_2 = 0 \rightarrow 0.02$. The corresponding volume fraction for the polypropylene fibres is then set to have the value $V_1 = 1 - V_2 - V_m$. The dependence of a matrix cracking stress ratio and an axial modulus ratio on the volume fraction of the glass fibres introduced into the polypropylene/cement composite is shown in Fig.1. It is seen that as the volume fraction of the additional glass fibres increases from 0 to 0.02, the modulus ratio increases by about 4% but the stress ratio for matrix cracking increases by about 73% indicating an extremely beneficial improvement in matrix cracking resistance.

Figure 1: Dependence of the modulus and matrix cracking stress ratios on the volume fraction of glass fibre in a hybrid uni-directional composite.

References

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